

What we mean by *research data*

A definition with explanations

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What does *research data* mean?

Multiple definitions of research data are or have been used by various national and international actors. These definitions are often tied to a particular actor's needs or to a specific context, and they are not easily transferred to another setting or situation. SND's definition of research data is adapted to our own operations and is intended, to the greatest extent possible, to be applicable independently of the methods, theories, epistemological perspectives, scales and scopes, organizational forms, and funding models under which research is conducted.

SND works with the following definition of *research data* (which is explained and elaborated on in detail below):

Research data are representations of phenomena that, on the basis of scientific principles, are deemed suitable for use in scientific or scholarly analysis, or for otherwise providing the basis for, or validating, research results. They have been compiled, collected, created, or otherwise generated as part of the research process.

Note: Research data may exist in digital or analogue formats and may come from research funded in different ways. SND works **primarily** with wholly or partially publicly funded research data in digital form, as well as with data intended for research.

Explanation

There is no single, unambiguous definition or shared understanding of the concept of research data.¹ To clarify what SND means by research data – in a way that is applicable across different academic disciplines and data practices – we cannot rely on the definitions of other key actors. The definition above is based on a broad understanding of what data and research are, has a theoretical foundation, and is intended to be applicable regardless of discipline. The different components of the definition are explained below.

Research data are representations of phenomena ...

Research data are material, that is, fixed to a digital or analogue medium, and can therefore be transferred between individuals.² "Phenomena" include, for example, living beings, objects, processes, or behaviours. Observations of phenomena are rendered as data when documented in various ways (i.e., made material), for example, by means of measuring instruments, personal notes, recordings, or images.³ Research data are thus not the phenomena themselves – that is, the being, behaviour, natural phenomenon, process, object, work, or other entity – but a fixed **representation** of them. Nor do research data include the metadata that describe relevant aspects of the data; however,

¹ Borgman (2012), pp. 1061, 1066, 1072; Thoegersen (2018), p. 501; Kvale (2022), pp. 18–19; Dutoit (2022), pp. 125, 128.

² Leonelli (2015), pp. 817–19.

³ Borgman (2012), pp. 1061, 1072; Borgman (2015), pp. 28, 63; Haider & Kjellberg (2016), pp. 144–45; Kvale (2022), p. 18.

what constitutes metadata in one context may constitute data in another, depending on which phenomenon is the object of research.

... that, on the basis of scientific principles, are deemed suitable ...

Determining whether something can serve as a basis for research is in itself a scholarly act,⁴ regardless of whether the data are intended for a specific research task or are only considered potentially useful for research. All data *may* be useful to some form of research, but identifying their potential to serve as research evidence is a scholarly act that renders them research data – even if they are never used. It is therefore less meaningful to ask **what** research data are than **when** research data are.⁵ The researcher performs a particularly important task in distinguishing information that is to be analysed from information that could be analysed but is not used.⁶ Jutta Haider and Sara Kjellberg describe this as “one person’s data is another’s technicality or noise”.⁷

... for use in scientific or scholarly analysis, or for otherwise providing the basis for, or validating, research results.

Science aims to generate new knowledge. Leonelli expresses this by stating that research data can be used as “evidence for claims about the world”,⁸ and the view of research data as part of scientific evidence-making is widely shared.⁹ In other definitions, research data are described as something that is “collected or generated for scientific analysis”,¹⁰ is “relating to research results”,¹¹ or “are used as evidence in the research process, or [...] to validate research findings and results.”¹² What these have in common is the idea that data can provide a basis for new knowledge or a means of assessing the extent to which existing knowledge is correct.

They have been compiled, collected, created, or otherwise generated ...

Research data may be produced in many different ways and originate from a wide range of sources.¹³ Regardless of how they are produced or come to form part of the research process, and regardless of how that process is described, they are included in this definition.

⁴ Borgman (2012), p. 1061; Borgman (2015), p. 62.

⁵ Borgman (2012), p. 1061; Borgman (2015), pp. 4–5, 17–18; Dutoit (2022), pp. 21–22.

⁶ Jacoby (1991), p. 4.

⁷ Kvale (2022), p. 19, citing Haider & Kjellberg (2016).

⁸ Leonelli (2015), p. 817.

⁹ E.g., Borgman (2015), p. 28; Thoegersen (2018), p. 498; Kvale (2022), p. 18.

¹⁰ “Rules for Research Data”, University of Gothenburg

¹¹ *Recommendation concerning the application of regulations with regard to the deletion/destruction and preservation of research information*, Association of Swedish Higher Education Institutions

¹² The Open Data Directive (Directive (EU) 2019/1024).

¹³ Borgman (2012), p. 1061, 1072; Kvale (2022), p. 18; cf. The Swedish Research Council, the University of Gothenburg, the Open Data Act, the Open Data Directive, the Swedish National Audit Office.

... as part of the research process.

Research may take different forms, but regardless of how it is conducted, it may produce research data. It does not matter under what circumstances they are produced: in a large, externally funded project spanning several years; in the limited research time available as part of regular duties, resulting in a single article after a few weeks; or in any other research context.

Examples of research data

Data differ depending on the type of research being conducted. According to Borgman, most research data in the natural sciences are created or collected by researchers, for example through observations, experiments, or models. In the social sciences, researchers may collect or generate their own data or use existing data sources, such as public records of economic activity. Borgman also notes that the concept of data is least developed in the humanities (although the development of digital humanities has made the term more common). Data in the humanities are primarily drawn from documentation of human culture, for example from archives, published documents, and artefacts.¹⁴

Definitions and descriptions provide the following examples of research data:

- 3D scans
- archival materials
- audiovisual materials
- images
- digital texts
- documentation of scientific and/or artistic processes
- survey data
- physical documents
- field notes
- instrument calibrations
- interview recordings
- codebooks
- measurements
- observational data
- software
- samples
- results from experiments and studies
- statistical data

... and several other types of digital objects.

Research without research data

Not all epistemic cultures – that is, approaches to how knowledge is produced, which may vary between research fields and academic disciplines – have research data in the sense of the definition given here. In some cases, observations are represented only in fragmentary or idiosyncratic ways, or a mixture of observation, analysis, and interpretation is documented. For example, much literary scholarship is based on observations of literary phenomena and their contexts, without such observations necessarily being formally or materially documented; analysis and interpretation are

¹⁴ Borgman (2012), p. 1061, with references to Borgman (2007) and Borgman (2009).

integrated into the act of observation itself, and the results are documented as notes or directly as research results. Other epistemic cultures, such as mathematics, are based primarily or exclusively on deductive reasoning, independently of empirical observations. It is also worth considering whether a literature review (systematic or otherwise) is based on data or whether it is (merely) a compilation of research results.

Works cited

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Appendix: Examples

The following excerpts provide a number of examples of other definitions of *research data*, for comparison and overview. These examples are not an attempt to collect all the definitions there are, nor to claim that these are the most important ones, but to offer a selection of variety of common definitions.

Examples of definitions from Swedish organizations

[The Swedish Research Council's recommendations for research data: FAIR and open access](#)

(2025: 8–9)

Research data: Data collected or produced within the framework of publicly funded scientific research activities. In this context, data refer to information in a digital format.

Comment: Data can, for example, consist of digital texts, images, audio-visual materials, 3D scans, observation data, results from experiments and other types of digital objects. The concept of research data also includes the metadata that describe research data and are aimed at making research data findable.

Existing data from other actors (such as public agency data) used in research are not always considered to be research data. Such data become research data if they are analysed, processed, or otherwise refined in a way that makes them a part of the research data that have been produced during the research process. Existing data that are already administered and made accessible by another actor and have been used in their original form in research are not covered by this definition.

University of Gothenburg, Rules for Research Data (GU 2025/422)

Research data includes all materials and information, regardless of format, that have been collected or generated for scientific analysis. This can range from interview recordings, images, and films to measurements, experimental results, physical documents, observations, or survey data. Research data may originate from quantitative as well as qualitative processes, and may consist of primary data gathered specifically for a research project or secondary data reused from previous studies

Swedish National Audit Office (Riksrevisionen): [Informationssäkerhet vid universitet och högskolor – hanteringen av skyddsvärda forskningsdata \(2023\)](#) (Information security at higher education institutions – management of research data requiring protection)

Research data refers to data that are collected or produced within the framework for scientific research activities. They may consist of digital texts, images, audiovisual material, 3D scans, observation data, results from experiments and other types of digital objects. (Translation taken from the Swedish Research Council (2023) below, as the Swedish original was the same.)

Swedish Research Council: [Indicators for open access to research data](#) (2023)

Research data refers to data that are collected or produced within the framework for scientific research activities.

They may consist of digital texts, images, audiovisual material, 3D scans, observation data, results from experiments and other types of digital objects.

The Open Data Act / [Lag \(2022:818\) om den offentliga sektorns tillgängliggörande av data](#)

“Research data refers in the law to data that to some extent is publicly funded, collected or produced within the framework for scientific research activities, and made directly accessible for further use via a publicly accessible data platform.” (Translation from information about the Act from the Swedish Research Council on [Making research data accessible and FAIR criteria](#) (accessed 2026-05-07).)

Association of Swedish Higher Education Institutions (SUHF): [Recommendation concerning the application of regulations with regard to the deletion/ destruction and preservation of research information](#)

Our view of research data

The working group chose to take an inclusive approach to defining research data, which resulted in the view that the term *research data* include all supporting documentation relating to research results. It can consist of everything from measurements, statistical data and interviews, to documentation of a scientific and/or artistic process that led to a research result.

Not all scientific or artistic disciplines use the term *data* but the working group has chosen to use the term *data* for all forms of supporting documentation for results from research with a scientific or artistic basis.

The working group believes that, rather than finding different terminology for different scientific or artistic disciplines, it is more important to try to broaden what we include in the term *data*. Not least because society and the research community place increasing demands on how we manage the supporting documentation for research results, through requirements for data management plans, or through incentives or requirements to make more than just the final results from the research process available.

For comparison:

The Open Data Directive / [Directive \(EU\) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information \(recast\)](#)

Article 2, definitions:

research data: ‘research data’ means documents in a digital form, other than scientific publications, which are collected or produced in the course of scientific research activities and are used as evidence in the research process, or are commonly accepted in the research community as necessary to validate research findings and results.

From Recital (27): [...] Research data includes statistics, results of experiments, measurements, observations resulting from fieldwork, survey results, interview recordings and images. It also includes meta-data, specifications and other digital objects. Research data is different from scientific articles reporting and commenting on findings resulting from their scientific research.
